

A reflection on methodological sensitivity, quality and transparency in the processing of new “big” data sources

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Abstract

In this discursive contribution we propose a general reflection on the statistical methodology development in the context of new, non-traditional data sources, often referred with the popular umbrella term of “big data”. The motivations and factors driving towards increasing complexity and *softwarization* of data processing are discussed along with the implications for methodological quality. It is argued that increased complexity induces a higher degree of sensitivity of the final results to a longer chain of methodological choices, thus requiring a more systematic approaches towards understanding and analysing *methodological sensitivity*. It is claimed that the statistical and scientific communities should develop new techniques and practices to incorporate *methodological sensitivity analysis* as a standard component of the statistical methodology development and scientific exploration processes.

Keywords: methodological transparency, methodological sensitivity; new data sources.

1. Statistics as a knowledge process

Generally speaking, given some generally *complex* real-world phenomenon z (e.g., social or economic) the goal of official statistics is to provide a *parsimonious* representation y that summarises the salient macroscopic aspects of phenomenon z in order to enable interpretation and action by humans. This is basically a reduction process, from complexity to parsimony, as depicted in Fig. 3(a). The final description y is intended to be interpreted, elaborated and possibly actioned by humans, e.g. for taking decisions, formulating policies and forming opinions that will ultimately feed back into the real world and influence the phenomenon z or the perception thereof. As humans can ingest only a limited amount of information detail, the description y must be parsimonious, i.e., reduced to a limited set of statistics and indicators. Reasoning and debating (collectively) about *what* metrics and indicators to choose, and *why* choosing them, is already an intrinsic part of the knowledge-building process about the phenomenon z that is embodied by the statistical process.

Even in the purely ideal case that the real-world phenomenon z could be known precisely and completely, with no errors or gaps, the choice of a suitable set of descriptive statistics and/or indicators would be a matter of design choice. In such ideal case, sketched in Fig. 3(a), no sources of error or measurement uncertainty are present (since there is no measurement process) but still there is an unavoidable degree of subjectivity in the definitions and choice of statistics and indicators, i.e., in the way the phenomenon of interest is represented. Such design choices need to be clearly documented (and motivated) in order to be discussed, agreed upon or criticised¹.

In practice, the real-world phenomenon cannot be known exactly and completely, and our knowledge of z is unavoidably mediated by a *measurement process* that generates *data* x that are then transformed into statistics and indicators y , as depicted in Fig. 3(b). In other words, the whole reduction process is segmented into two stages: the intermediate measurement data x capture only part of the (generally more complex) phenomenon z , and the final statistics represent only a summary view of the (generally more detailed) data x . Furthermore, in addition to *information* related to z , the measurement data x contain also measurement errors, ambiguities and uncertainties of different kinds, including both systematic and casual effects.

It should be noted that humans are involved on all sides of this process: on the input side, as constituent parts of the phenomenon z to be measured (data subjects); on the output side, as recipients of the statistical information y that is produced (statistical users); and on the throughput side, in the role of specialists and experts deciding upon the description process (e.g., statisticians, scientists).

2. From questions for humans to instructions for machines

When the measurement process consists of surveys and censuses, statisticians and domain experts are in full control of (equivalently: have the possibility to design) both the *data generation* and the *data processing* stages. The methodological design choices can be optimally divided between these two modules: which questions to ask (questionnaire design) and to whom (sample design) are determined in the data generation module that produces a set of micro-data. In the next

¹Like in other branches of human activities, including science, when consensus is achieved among experts some design options become conventionally accepted and eventually consolidate into more or less formal norms and practices. Eventually, they are encoded into manuals, textbooks and technical documents. Such consensus consolidation process, however, does not make the preferred design choices become *objective*, absolutely true and free from limitations. Maintaining a vigilant critical view on established design options, and on the motivations for their adoption in a specific context, is necessary not only to eventually modify them (e.g. due to a change of context or paradigm) but also to correctly interpret their results while they are in force. The discussion and critical review of statistical methods, definitions and indicators is at the very core of the knowledge-building process embodied by official statistics.

(a) Statistical description as a reduction process from a complex phenomenon to a parsimonious set of statistics and indicators.

(b) Statistical description mediated by measurement data

Figure 1: Information reduction process from phenomenon z to statistics y through data x

data processing stage, the micro-data are transformed into a set of aggregate statistics and indicators.

In the context of statistics based on survey and census data, measurement errors are typically counteracted at both stages, with preventive and reactive measures, respectively, at the data generation and data processing stages (ref. Fig. 3(b)). Furthermore, the data generation process in this case involves responses formulated by humans (data subjects, respondents) to questions formulated by other humans (statisticians and domain experts). In this way, at the individual level, the human respondent concurs with the statistical expert to reduce the complexity of his/her individual behaviour so as to fit it into the model that, implicitly or explicitly, was adopted by the survey designer². We note that there are two levels of subjective choices in this process: (i) the subjective judgement of the respondent in formulating the answer (at micro level), and (ii) the subjective judgement of the questionnaire designer in formulating the question (at macro level). An additional element of subjective choice occurs (iii) in the subjective judgement of the specialist in charge of designing the data processing method (e.g., which particular imputation method is adopted out of the many existing variants, in which way the data are aggregated, which summary indicator is selected etc.).

Moving from survey to administrative data sources, statisticians lose the possibility of influencing the data generation process, that now corresponds to the administrative procedure

²For example, if the survey asks to identify the “main location” of residence, a respondent that divides its time equally among two or more locations would be forced to select *subjectively* a single location, based on its subjective interpretation of what “main location” means. Also, asking about the number of “touristic trips” leaves to the respondent the responsibility to interpret whether a mixed trip, conducted for business reasons but including a touristic detour or extension, would be counted as “touristic” or not.

in place to serve administrative, not statistical purposes. Still, the human element in the production of the data x is kept: it is still the data subject to declare where his/her “main place” of living is located or the “reason for travelling”, though this declaration is now given to an administrative authority in the context of some administrative procedure, rather than being given in response to a statistical survey. Since the data generation process is now out of their control, statisticians cannot influence explicitly the kinds and amount of measurement error affecting the data x . Therefore, in order to counteract measurement errors, they can act exclusively on the data processing stage, and this adds complexity to the latter.

This trend goes even further when moving to new kinds of digital data sources, often termed “non-traditional” (from the perspective of official statistics) or “big” data sources. These data are often generated by digital machines that interact directly with the human subjects or monitor them indirectly. Examples of such data include e.g. credit card transactions, location data from mobile phone apps, social network posts and a plethora of other kinds of digital traces created, directly or indirectly, by digital systems. Compared to the case of traditional survey/census data, the following elements contribute to make the design of the data processing stage considerably more complex for such “new” data sources:

- Lack of control over the design of data generation process implies that all countermeasures against measurement errors are pushed to the data processing stage. In other words, as the data generation system is *given as is* and cannot be influenced by the statisticians, all methodological design choices get loaded into the data processing stage.
- The effective design of such countermeasures must be based on a deep understanding of the data generation system, particularly in the technological and behavioural aspects thereof. For example, in case of location data collected by the mobile network operator (MNO), understanding the operational dynamics of the mobile network infrastructure, and particularly of the radio access section thereof, requires a certain amount of engineering knowledge and skills that fall outside the traditional profile of professional statisticians. Therefore, the development of effective data processing methodologies requires establishing multi-disciplinary teams with statisticians and technology-specific experts (from the business sector concerned) collaborating together.
- The changing nature of the data generation system, following the physiological evolution of the underlying technologies, business and behaviours³ induces a continuous change in the

³Examples of evolutionary lines affecting the MNO data generation process include e.g. the evolution of mobile technologies from 2G (GSM) to 3G (UMTS) and 4G (LTE); the transition from consumption-based to flat-rate mobile tariffs; the advent of smartphones and data apps in smartphones.

characteristics of the data x . This in turn calls for an *evolvable* approach to the design of data processing methods, based on highly modular and carefully designed *methodological frameworks and architectures* that can accommodate for flexibility and adaptation of detailed methods and parameters thereof (methodological evolvability by design).

- The automated nature of data generation implies that the data subject is observed passively by the data generation system. The subjective element that was at the core of the data generation process based on survey or administrative procedures, namely the human judgement by the data subject (i.e., interpretation of the question by the respondent) is now missing. This implies that the whole responsibility of defining a criterion for translating a qualitative concept into a machine-readable code falls on the designer of the data processing methodology. For example, it is now up to the methodologist to decide the criteria for identifying which locations are to be classified as constituting the data subject’s “usual environment”, which one is to be elected “main location”, which ones of his/her trips are to be considered “frequent” or “regular”, etc. As such criteria are now executed by the machines (instead of being interpreted by human respondents) they must be *encoded in the language of machines, i.e. in software code*⁴.

3. Softwarization of statistical methodologies

As discussed above, when new “big” data sources are used to produce statistics, the data design phase is missing and the statistical methodology reduces to data processing. Due to their large volumes and rates, new data sources must be processed automatically, and consequently the statistical methodology must be translated into software code. Data processing methods for new data sources tend to be rather complex, for the reasons discussed above. Most of the new data sources tend to be generated by machines that interact with humans, and their correct interpretation requires understanding of behavioural as well as technological aspects. Furthermore, such data are often characterised by various kinds of uncertainty and errors that must be handled properly in the data processing stage, some of which have no direct correspondence with those typical of traditional data sources. For this reason, understanding and coping with new data sources requires specialist knowledge from fields outside the traditional perimeter of statistics. All the above means that the development of statistical methodologies for new data sources goes tightly hand in hand with the development of complex software code

⁴However, the code-level description does not eliminate the need to represent them *also* in forms that are suitable for interpretation and review (and possibly improvement) by other human experts.

by multidisciplinary teams. The *softwarization* of statistical methodologies yields important consequences on how methodologies are developed, evaluated and communicated.

The first obvious consequence is an increasing need by methodological departments to acquire skills and learn (and apply) best practices from software development specialists. The design of a complex methodology become closely intermingled with the design of the data processing software that implements that methodology. In other words, methodology design and methodological software design cannot be easily decoupled and should best addressed jointly by a single team of methodologists and software architects working side-by-side.

Second, the softwarization of statistical methodology requires to import established concepts, methods and practices from *software quality* into *statistical quality* frameworks.

Third, the principle of methodological transparency, casted in a context where methodologies are embodied into software, points to the necessity to release open-source the software code that implements the methodology along with proper documentation. Indeed, to the extent that a piece of software f implements the data processing stage that transforms the input data x into output statistics y (formally $f : x \mapsto y$ or equivalently $\langle f, x \rangle \rightarrow y$) the source code of f should be considered as an essential component of the process “meta-data” for y . In other words, the complete and non-ambiguous knowledge of the method f , through its open-source code, becomes a necessary pre-condition for the correct interpretation of the statistical result y .

4. Closed-loop vs open-loop data analysis

In parallel to the softwarization of statistical methodologies, the increasing complexity of the data processing stage amplifies the need to understand, handle and communicate properly the issue of *methodological sensitivity*. In order to introduce and elaborate the issue in the subsequent sections, we preliminarily reflect on the different possible ways by which the design of data processing method evolves in scientific disciplines, and specifically on the distinction between “closed-loop” and “open-loop” data analysis cycles, as depicted in Figure 2.

Our focus here is on scientific disciplines and application fields relying on the analysis (processing) of some data x originated from some real-world phenomenon z , with the analysis result $y = f(x)$ obtained through an analysis method f and serving some particular purpose. In some application contexts, the “goodness of fit” of result y to the specific purpose can be verified or anyway assessed *ex post* in some way (e.g., based on reference data or experimental testing). In such cases, the positive or negative outcome of the verification process provides a “feedback signal” that drives the further improvement and future evolution of the analysis methodology f . In other words, the data analysis step is embedded into a “closed-loop” learning

(a) Closed-loop analysis: the goodness of the final result y can be verified in some way and the outcome of the verification process provides feedback to the design of the analysis method $f()$. In this way, different methodological options can be compared and the best one(s) selected, resulting in a continuous improvement of the analysis method.

(b) Open-loop analysis: there is no practical way to assess directly the goodness of the final result y .

Figure 2: Closed-loop versus open-loop data analysis.

process, as depicted in Figure 2(a). Such learning loops may occur at different levels and scales. For instance, at the level of individual researcher or research team, the (positive or negative) feedback signal from the verification process drives the methodological choices and allows to select the variant of the analysis method that is best fit for the task at hand. At the level of the whole research community, the feedback drives the selection of the best methodological approach when different approaches are proposed concurrently by different research teams.

In some application domains, the verification (or validation) process is expensive and cumbersome, e.g. in computational medicine it may require setting up a clinical trial involving tens of patients for several months. In such cases, the methodological learning loop occurs at the human level and is *slow*. In other application domains, the validation process is cheaper and can be (partially or fully) automated, e.g. when it is based on large amounts of labelled data serving as “training data set”. In such cases, if the space of possible methodological options (or

subspace thereof) can be fully or partially subsumed by the state space of some general-purpose numeric tool, e.g., a neural network, we end up with (supervised) Machine Learning (ML) methods. In general, in most scientific disciplines nowadays we can identify a combination of automated and *fast* learning loops at machine level (e.g., training a neural network) with *slow* methodological learning loops occurring at the human level (e.g., opting for some structure or variety of neural network) both individually (single data scientist or team) and collectively (the whole scientific community). At the bottom of all these scientific disciplines is the possibility of assessing empirically the *goodness of fit* of the analysis method f through validation of the analysis result $y = f(x)$, as depicted in Fig. 2(a).

In other application domains, it is practically impossible to carry out a definitive validation process, and there is no immediate way to create a (slow or fast) feedback signal. This is often the case where the goal is to measure some large-scale phenomenon, for which no absolute “ground truth” reference exist. Consider for example the problem considered in Ricciato et al. (2020) of estimating the spatial distribution of people in a large region (e.g., a city or a whole country) at a given reference time from the data collected by a mobile network operator. There is no practical way to measure precisely where *all* people were at that precise moment throughout a large area of interest. We have different estimates obtained with different methodological options but how can we tell which one is the most accurate? We can resort to testing with synthetic data and reason on the ability (or lack thereof) of the methodology to account for known aspects and features of the data x that we deem to be relevant, but in doing so we end up assessing subjective choices (in the methodology design) with other subjective choices (in the design of synthetic data, in what we consider “relevant”). We can prove that one method is “optimal” or “better” than another with respect to a formal model, but again the choice of one or another model to capture the “important” characteristics of the real-world phenomenon z and/or data x entails other subjective choices. All these actions may well be considered as inherent part of the (subjective) methodological design process, rather than a (objective) assessment of its product methodology.

In cases where the possibility of direct objective verification/validation is absent, the data analysis module plays in the “open-loop” regime depicted in Fig. 2(b). For application domains and scientific disciplines in this regime, methodological evolution may be slower due to increased difficulty to discriminate “better” methodological options. In other words, the selection pressure⁵ is weaker and the “best” methodologies are less likely to be immediately recognised as such. This is not to say that methodological advancement does not occur in these fields, but it can be

⁵Note the analogy with natural selection pressure in ecology.

reasonably expected to progress at slower pace⁶.

5. Building trust in the open-loop methodological development regime

The lack of an explicit direct verification/validation process begs the question of why and to what extent we can trust the result y . A more constructive formulation of the same issue is: What measures should be put in place, individually and collectively, to produce *trustworthy results* in scientific contexts operating in the open-loop regime?

In order to attempt an answer, we should first recognise that (i) trusting the analysis result y , (ii) trusting the analysis method f and (iii) trusting the analysts (i.e., the scientists or specialist determining the analysis method) are closely interconnected but distinct aspects. And they all need to be addressed in parallel⁷.

The first measure is ensuring that the analysts (the statisticians in official statistics) are trustworthy. In the context of official statistics this is pursued by an institutional and legal setting aimed at guaranteeing professional independence and impartiality, that are regarded as key principles of official statistics by the UNSD *Fundamental Principles of Official Statistics* (2014). In the European Statistical System (ESS) such principles are encoded in the *European Statistics Code of Practice* (2018) and their actual application is reinforced by a system of institutional peer reviews⁸.

The second measure is ensuring that the analysis method is trustworthy. To this aim, the analysis method should be open, fully transparent and auditable. It should be unambiguously documented and all big and small methodological choices therein should be declared explicitly, and possibly motivated. In a context where data processing is performed by software, as in the case of *softwarized* statistical methodology discussed earlier in Section 3., it is natural to expect that the practical application of the general principles of transparency and auditability shall

⁶Other social dynamics in the research community may concur to make progress even slower, e.g. self-reinforcing *reputational effects* may be more easily at play in fields with open-loop regimes. At the level of a whole research community, lacking a sound and objective methodological validation/verification process, methodological approaches proposed by highly reputed teams enjoy even stronger competitive advantage over approaches proposed by less reputed teams, irrespective of their actual quality. Coupled with the self-reinforcing nature of the social mechanisms of reputation building, this leads to an interesting inversion of the causal relationship between (perceived) quality and reputation, whereby the former becomes the logical consequent, rather than the logical antecedent of the latter.

⁷In the context of official statistics we could specialise the terminology, and refer to “statistics” y , “statistical methodology” f and “statistician” instead of, respectively, “analysis result”, “analysis method” and “analyst”. However, as the following considerations are relevant also for other scientific disciplines, and not specific for official statistics, we prefer to retain a more general terminology to the benefit of a wider pool of potential readers in scientific communities beyond official statistics.

⁸See e.g. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/quality/peer-reviews>.

translate into the systematic release as public open-source code of the software components implementing the analysis/statistical methodology of choice, along with a thorough documentation. In several scientific fields, the availability of open-source code (and when possible of open data) is now considered a necessary prerequisite for ensuring replicability/reproducibility and therefore credibility of the results. The quest for increasing methodological transparency through a more systematic release of open-source code is making its way also in official statistics [Stodden \(2014\)](#), [Grazzini et al. \(2018\)](#).

These measures are very well present in the public debate around “data” and “science”, and they are being increasingly adopted across multiple scientific disciplines, although with varying degrees of maturity. On top of all that, we argue that an additional measure should be considered by the scientific and statistical communities in order to reinforce trust in the analysis result, related to the need to recognise and systematically address the issue of *methodological sensitivity*.

6. Methodological sensitivity

By *methodological sensitivity* we mean the degree by which the analysis result y depends (is sensitive to) different methodological design choices in f for the same input data x . The concept may be seen as a generalisation of the notion of *parameter sensitivity* that is addressed by classic *sensitivity analysis*. With the latter, the analyst explores the robustness of the final result to the setting of (some of) the key parameters encountered in the analysis methodology. But setting the value of some parameter(s) is just a small fraction of the plethora of methodological design choices that are taken at various levels and stages in the design of any data processing methodology. In the same spirit as the classical (parameter) sensitivity analysis explores the impact on the output y of different parameter settings, the more general *methodological sensitivity analysis* should aim at understanding the influence on the final result of a wider set of methodological choices and variants, beyond merely the value of a handful of parameters.

To illustrate, consider a data processing pipeline that at some stage involves the execution of some clustering procedure⁹ on the intermediate data produced by previous stages before passing the resulting data to the next stage. Let us assume that the choice of the clustering algorithm is not the main focus of the research, and it is merely one among many other methodological design choices in the path from input x to output y . In such a setting, the vast majority of research papers do not go beyond the choice of a single clustering algorithm (among the many possible

⁹The same consideration made here for clustering methods applies e.g. to imputation methods, outlier filtering criteria, choice of estimator, aggregation method, and virtually any other data analysis operation.

(a) Low methodological sensitivity

(b) High methodological sensitivity.

Figure 3: Methodological sensitivity.

options) and fix its parameters to a single set of values. The research paper gets published as long as the choices made by the analyst (about the clustering algorithm and parameters thereof, among others) look “reasonable” to the peer reviewers. A more thorough piece of research would delve into classic (parameter) sensitivity analysis, exploring the impact on the final result of changes (variations, perturbations) to some key parameter values within the same clustering algorithm. With a full fledged methodological sensitivity analysis, the analyst should perform a wider exploration of different methodological variants, testing multiple clustering algorithms and each algorithm with different parameter settings. And the same would be done for several other methodological modules upstream and downstream the data processing pipeline.

At the bottom of this proposal is the consideration that the design of an articulated data processing pipeline involves a sequence of methodological choices (Which clustering algorithm to adopt at this module? What filtering criterion to implement in that module? How to set their parameters?). For each methodological choice, or decision point, there are often multiple

concurrent options that appear equally “reasonable” to the specialist or scientist for the case at hand. The standard approach is to pick just a single option and then move to the next decision point. In this way, decision point by decision point, the analyst walks a single path within the hypothetical tree of all possible combinations of (equally reasonable) alternatives at each decision point. In other words, the analyst “samples” a single point in the space of all possible methodological options¹⁰, as represented in Fig. 4.

Let us consider the following mental experiment. We take a dozen different research teams, equally qualified (or at least equally reputed in their community), assign them the very same analysis task (e.g., measure the actual reduction in urban mobility after the introduction of Covid-19 containment actions by the government) and provide them with the very same input data set x (e.g., a large set of mobile network operator data). The only rule is that teams should work independently, with no interaction between each other. The teams will likely develop different methods and produce somewhat different results. But how different are the results produced by the different teams? If all results are coherent and roughly similar, then we are in a case of *low methodological sensitivity* as depicted in Fig. 3(a). In this case, the result is shown to be robust to the different *subjective* methodological choices operated by the different experts, hence we can conclude that y represents genuine feature of the phenomenon under study z as captured by data x (or at least, a genuine feature of the data x). In other words, if all different methods tell basically the same story, we can safely trust the story.

In the opposite scenario depicted in Fig. 3(b), the results obtained by the different teams are highly dispersed. In this case, the result is shown to be sensitive (or volatile) to the different methodological choices, and method diversity translates into result inconsistency. Recall that, by construction of the mental experiment, all methods are equally trustworthy in the sense of being designed by equally qualified (or more precisely: equally reputed) scientific teams. In the open-loop regime there is no way to select one or the other result (or method), and any statement made about z or x based on the results of any of these analyses is somewhat hazardous. If different equally reputable methods tell different stories, which one shall we trust?

In such a situation we could let the different teams mutually review and discuss the various methodologies, in a sort of deliberative methodological review process. Perhaps some methodological options will be recognised to be fallacious and will be dropped, or modified, and perhaps this will lead to higher degree of coherence among the surviving options. Or maybe

¹⁰In certain scientific contexts the “sampled” point may not be completely free from so-called *confirmation bias*. This aspect falls outside the scope of our discussion here and will not be elaborated further in this contribution. However, when confirmation bias is brought into the equation, it will further reinforce and add urgency to the conclusion of this reflection, that performing a more systematic methodological sensitivity analysis is a necessity that needs to be addressed in science and in statistics dealing with “big” data.

Figure 4: Traditional methodological design process as selection of a single point in the methodological space. Performing a systematic methodological sensitivity analysis means testing multiple points, i.e. a subset methodological variants. It is obviously impossible (and probably also unnecessary) to explore *all* methodological variants, even if we restrict attention to the subset of those that appear “reasonable” to qualified experts. But the unfeasibility of *testing all points* is no justification for *testing a single point*. Testing multiple points (more than one, but not all) is absolutely feasible and beneficial to the progress of science

not. In any case, such deliberative methodological process would provide rich insight and would constitute an important component of the knowledge-building process. Insight and knowledge that is normally just missed when a single method is proposed by a single team, instead of a dozen.

The cases exemplified in Fig. 3 assume the final result to be a single number, i.e. a scalar. In many real-world applications, the result is expressed in a more articulated form, e.g. as a distribution (unidimensional or multi-dimensional, e.g. a spatial map) or as an order statistics (ranking), and some parts thereof will be more robust (e.g., distribution mass, top-rank elements) and others more sensitive (e.g., distribution tails, low-rank elements) to methodological choices. Also in this case the deliberative methodological debate spurring from the comparison of the differences and commonalities between the results (and the methods) of different teams would create more valuable insight and deeper knowledge (also) on the phenomenon z than any individual team taken independently.

The mental experiment where multiple different teams draw different conclusions *from the same data set* may seem intellectually intriguing but not very realistic. It turns out that such kind of experiment was actually conducted for real, and the outcome (not surprisingly) was quite similar to the “high sensitivity” case of Fig. 3(b), see [Silberzahn et al. \(2018\)](#), [Schweinsberg et al. \(2021\)](#). This rises a number of important epistemological considerations that, however, fall outside the scope of this contribution.

7. A vision for the future

Recruiting multiple different teams for a single data analysis task is perhaps impractical and too costly. It is natural to ask whether methodological sensitivity analysis can be performed in a more practical and cheaper way. The softwarization of analysis methods may turn useful (also) in this respect, as the exploration of multiple methodological variants can be natively “embedded” into the software code, with appropriate software design patterns and support from programming languages and platforms that, however, are largely to be yet developed.

We claim that, in official statistics as well as scientific fields where data analysis operates in open-loop regimes, methodologies and data processing code should be developed taking into account systematically, and at early design phase, the requirement to enable and facilitate the exploration of multiple methodological variants on the same input data (methodological sensitivity analysis by design).

Performing some degree of methodological sensitivity analysis should become a common standard practice, rather than a rare exception, in the science business (methodological sensitivity analysis by default). Publishing and making claims about results obtained with a single data processing method, without checking their robustness to some decent number of methodological variations, should be perceived as a poor scientific practice by researchers and research managers.

Research teams should be encouraged not only to design and release their code in order to enable other researchers to *reproduce* their methodology, but to design and release code that is structured so as to enable other researchers to add and test new methodological variants, i.e., to *expand* their work. To this aim, methodologies and software pipelines for data processing should be structured in a highly modular way, with clear interfaces between the modules and the possibility to test multiple alternative solutions in each module.

The “mindset” of scientists and statisticians should be oriented to identify, implement and test, for each module in a larger methodological pipeline, more than a single reasonable solution (method, algorithm), and for each parameter, a continuous range or discrete set of “reasonable” values. The corresponding code would represent a tree of different methodological paths that can be explored, partially or exhaustively, depending on the available computing resources. The code should be designed, structured and documented not only to allow other researchers to *reproduce* the same methodological path, but to further *expand* the methodological tree by adding other options at each methodological decision point. New functions could be developed in popular programming languages to facilitate the implementation and testing of multiple methodological paths (multi-methodology programming). Moving from a single to multiple methodological paths, innovative methods will be needed to present, visualise and make sense of

the collection of multiple results, for the same analysis task and from the very same input data.

Finally, the the development of new tools and practices should go hand in hand with changing the mindset of researchers and statisticians, from pursuing the Holy Grail of a *single* “best”, or at least “good enough” methodology, towards the exploration of reasonably wide set of alternative methodologies.

Testing a diverse set of methodological variants helps to recognise and counteract the potential effect of (benign) methodological artefacts on the final result. It helps to understand how much of the final results is “extracted” from the data, and how much instead is “crafted” by methodological choice(s). This is more important than ever in the context of “big” data, as the increasing complexity of data processing methodologies, due to reasons discussed earlier in Section 2., leads to a proliferation of methodological decision points and amplifies the risk of mistakes and fallacies in the design and/or implementation of the data processing methodology, even by the most qualified expert. More in general, we conjecture that the increase in methodological complexity induces an increase in methodological sensitivity, and therefore amplifies the urgency to account for it in methodological development process.

References

European Statistics Code of Practice (2018). Revised edition 2017.

URL: <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-catalogues/-/KS-02-18-142>

Fundamental Principles of Official Statistics (2014).

URL: <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/dnss/gp/fundprinciples.aspx>

Grazzini, J., Lamarche, P., Gaffuri, J. & Museux, J.-M. (2018), Show me your code, and then I will trust your figures: Towards software-agnostic open algorithms in statistical production, in ‘New Techniques and Technologies for Statistics (NTTS) conference’. <https://zenodo.org/record/3240282#.XbsCCVTPw6g>.

Ricciato, F., Lanzieri, G., Wirthmann, A. & Seynaeve, G. (2020), ‘Towards a methodological framework for estimating present population density from mobile network operator data’, *Pervasive and Mobile Computing* **68**, 101–263.

URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1574119220301097>

Schweinsberg et al. (2021), ‘Same data, different conclusions: Radical dispersion in empirical results when independent analysts operationalize and test the same hypothesis’, *Organizational*

Behavior and Human Decision Processes **165**, 228–249.

URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0749597821000200>

Silberzahn et al. (2018), ‘Many analysts, one data set: making transparent how variations in analytic choices affect results’, *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science* **1**(3), 337–356.

URL: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2515245917747646>

Stodden, V. (2014), ‘The reproducible research movement in statistics’, *Statistical Journal of the IAOS* **30**. [doi:10.3233/SJI-140818](https://doi.org/10.3233/SJI-140818).